

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Particles track from model and observations: A contribution to the OCEAN ICE work packages WP1 and WP2

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History of Changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	25 September 2025	Submitted version	Igor Brovchenko
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1. Publishable summary

This deliverable aims to assess the connectivity of currents around the Antarctic Peninsula, identify the structure of flows carrying particles from the Eastern to Western Antarctic Peninsula continental shelves through the Bransfield Strait, and ice keel-induced breaking of internal solitary waves (ISW). For the first two tasks, we utilised circulation data from the Weddell and Bellingshausen Seas in the Whole Antarctica Ocean Model (WAOM) to obtain and analyse particle trajectories using the Parcels model. For the third task, the non-hydrostatic model was applied. The pathways of water masses were characterised by calculating Lagrangian statistical parameters: the visitation frequency and the representative trajectory. The visitation frequency is the percentage of particles P that visit each 10×10 km grid column at least once during a 20-year modelling period. The representative particle trajectory is the individual particle trajectory that deviates the least from the rest of the individual trajectories. The latter characteristic was first introduced in oceanography. The proportion of particles that turn to the Bellingshausen Sea is 21% of the total number of particles, while 70% turn northeast, and the proportion of remaining on the shelf is 9%. The farther to the west, the more particles are captured by the strong ACC. So, only 3.4% of the particles were transported west of 80°W , while only 0.1% reached the Amundsen Sea (105°W). This indicates a lack of connectivity between Weddell and Amundsen Seas circulation. In the Bransfield Strait, the representative trajectories align well with the distributions of visitation frequencies. They demonstrate essential dependence on the release season and the release depth. The wavelet analysis of recent high-resolution ice keel survey data collected during the MOSAIC expedition (<https://mosaic-expedition.org/>), which utilised a multi-beam sonar mounted on a remotely operated vehicle, revealed that the mean keel width can be categorised into two distinct classes. In the first class, the keel width was 30–40 m in summer and winter. In another class, the zone of pressure ridging can be much larger, ranging from 60 to 110 m. Another result of high-resolution measurements was the discovery of a fine structure of ridging zones with “sub-keels” of several meter scale that contribute to the ridge roughness, enhancing mixing by ISW. The shorter ISW wavelengths, relative to the keel, lead to more intense wave–keel interactions, resulting in enhanced wave breaking, vortex formation, turbulent dissipation, and sea ice melting. Similarly, a shorter distance between keels at a fixed horizontal scale of the ridge results in enhancing the dissipation of ISW.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Study of the connectivity of currents between the Weddell and Bellingshausen Seas using particle tracking

The Antarctic Peninsula (AP), which extends approximately 1300 km into the Southern Ocean, effectively separates the systems of shelf currents along its eastern and western coasts. In particular, the Antarctic Slope Current (ASC) disappears on both sides of the AP (Thompson et al., 2018). The barrier effect and differences in topography lead to significant changes in the circulation off the coasts of Western and Eastern Antarctic Peninsula (WAP and EAP, respectively). While the AP shields the currents on the Weddell Sea shelf from the effect of ACC, the currents on the Bellingshausen Sea shelf interact with the southern boundary of the ACC (Moffat and Meredith, 2018). The southern Weddell Sea shelf can be divided into a relatively narrow EAP

shelf and a wide shelf with the Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf (FRIS). The WAP can be divided into the Bransfield Strait and the central WAP (Moffat and Meredith, 2018). The Bransfield Strait, between the South Shetland Islands and the AP, is a deep basin with a complex cyclonic circulation pattern. The Antarctic Coastal Current (ACoC) enters the Bransfield Strait around the AP tip, transporting about 1 Sv (Heywood et al., 2004). Then it propagates along the Peninsula into the Bellingshausen Sea.

Fig. 1: Map and the bathymetry of the Weddell and Bellingshausen Antarctic Peninsula sectors, showing ice shelves (white line). The scale shows the depth. MT is the Marguerite Trough, BT is the Belgica Trough. Filled circles show the locations of particle release in the areas adjacent to the Ronne-Filchner (red) and Larsen (green) Ice Shelves. The dashed line shows the computational domain of the WAOM. Orange solid lines show cross sections at 58°, 70° and 80°W.

The analysis performed in the project aimed to assess the connectivity of currents around the AP and to identify the structure of flows that carry virtual particles from the EAP to the WAP shelves. We used circulation data for the Weddell and Bellingshausen Seas, calculated by the circulation model: “Whole Antarctica Ocean Model” (WAOM) (Richter et al., 2022), to obtain and analyse particle trajectories using “Probably A Really Computationally Efficient Lagrangian Simulator” (Parcels) model (Delandmeter and van Sebille, 2019). The WAOM circulation model is based on the Regional Ocean Modelling System (ROMS version 3.6), a free-surface, terrain-following, primitive equations ocean model. The new kernels updated the particle-tracking model Parcel to recover lost particles and to represent the convection, which was not explicitly described in the surface mixed layer (Maderich et al., 2024). In contrast to other Lagrangian models, we can track virtual particles under ice shelves.

In total, approximately 170,000 virtual particles were released at a depth of 10 m over the course of a year, with a spatial step of 1°, in two shelf and slope sectors of the southern Weddell Sea, where the depth is less than 1500 m (Fig. 1). The first sector covers a shelf area between 71°S and 77°S adjacent to the Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf. The second sector covers a shelf area between 70°S and 65°S adjacent to the Larsen Ice

Shelf. The visitation frequency and representative trajectories characterised the pathways of water masses. The **visitation frequency** is the percentage of particles P that visit each 10×10 km grid column at least once during a 20-year modelling period. The **representative particle trajectory** is the individual particle trajectory that deviates the least from the rest of the individual trajectories. The Lock-step Euclidean Distance method, based on the average distance between all pairs of temporally corresponding particle positions, was used for its calculation. Here, the representative particle trajectory concept was first introduced in oceanography.

Fig. 2 shows the WAOM summer and winter velocity components perpendicular to the FRIS front, with positive values corresponding to the FRIS inflow. The modelled velocities are consistent with the observational data, exhibiting an inflow off the west coast at 61°W , an outflow at 60°W in winter, and an outflow throughout the year from under the Ronne Ice Shelf at $58^\circ\text{--}57^\circ\text{W}$. Further to the east, between 56°W and 48°W , inflow and outflow zones alternate along the ice front. The outflow through the Filchner Trough is between 38 and 40°W , while inflows occur at its edges. As seen in Fig. 2, the water exchange through the Ronne Ice Front is more substantial in winter.

The visitation frequency P [%] calculated for all released particles on the Weddell Sea shelf is shown in Figure 3a. This figure demonstrates how particles released on the shelf propagate by currents toward the tip of AP. The distribution of visitation frequency on the Weddell Sea shelf shows the presence of maxima corresponding to intense cross-shelf currents flowing from beneath the Ronne Ice Shelf (RIS) and transporting ice shelf water (Maderich et al., 2024). Additionally, in the western part of the RIS, water enters beneath the ice shelf, spreading out beneath it and the Filchner Ice Shelf (FIS). A significant portion of the particles is transported by ASC along the shelf break to the north, after which the flux of particles is split to the east and west. The eastward part of the flow corresponds to a deepening water mass—a precursor to Antarctic Abyssal Bottom Water (AABW). The splitting location agrees with the results of drifter experiments (Thompson et al., 2009). The proportions of particles crossing 58°W (the tip of the Antarctic Peninsula), 70°W , 80°W , and 105°W are given in Table 1. The proportion of particles that turn to the Bellingshausen Sea is 21% of the total number of particles, while 70% turn northeast, and the proportion of remaining on the shelf is 9%.

Table 1: Percentage of particles crossing the cross-sections at the shelf of the Bellingshausen Sea.

Source sector	Remained in the Weddell Sea	58°W	70°W	80°W	105°W
Green	0.04	51	20	8.4	0.3
Red	11	14	5.4	2.2	0.04
All	9	21	8.4	3.4	0.1

Fig. 2: Velocity components perpendicular to the FRIS front in summer (a) and winter (b). The views are northward, looking out from the sub-ice cavity. Positive values correspond to inflow, and negative values correspond to outflow. Orange and blue vertical arrows approximately correspond to the locations of observed inflows and outflows, respectively. Numbers 1, 3, and 5 mark the locations of inflows/outflows of Janout et al. (2021), 2 marks the location of Foldvik et al. (2001), 4 is the location of Gammelsrød et al. (1994), 6 is the location of Darelius and Sallée (2018), and 7 is the approximate location of (Darelius et al, 2014; Hattermann et al., 2021).

Fig. 3: (a) Visitation frequency P [%] calculated for all released particles on the Weddell Sea shelf; (b) P for particles that crossed 58°W ; (c) P for particles that crossed 70°W .

Figure 3b shows the distribution of visitation frequency for particles crossing 58°W . These particles move west along the WAP in the ACoC and then turn around to flow through the Bransfield Strait along the east coast of the South Shetland Islands. About 74% of particles flow in the upper 400 m layer. In this case, the contribution of green and red particles is approximately equal. Such a distribution of particles by depth indicates that the transport of ACoC is controlled by a relatively shallow coastal shelf at the AP tip. This issue requires further study, both using floats and modelling at higher spatial resolution. Only 8.4% of particles crossed 70°W (Fig. 3c). Figure 3c shows the distribution of visitation frequency for these particles, showing that most of them return to Drake Passage. These particles penetrate deep into the straits and bays of the WAP through the Marguerite and Belgica Troughs, similarly to drifters in experiments by Schubert et al. (2021). The farther to the west, the more particles are captured by the strong ACC. So, only 3.4% of the particles were transported west of 80°W , while only 0.1% reached the Amundsen Sea (105°W). This indicates a lack of connectivity between Weddell and Amundsen Seas circulation.

Fig. 4: Vertical transect between the ice shelf (cyan) and the seabed (grey) following the representative trajectory (blue line) for the category of particles released in summer at 350 m and leaving FRIS through the Filchner Through. (b) The corresponding evolution of conservative temperature (red line) and absolute salinity (blue line) of a virtual particle. Plots (c) and (d) are as (a) and (b) but for particles released in winter. A sudden increase in the depth of particles is highlighted in Fig. 4a and 4c by red circles. The zoom map corresponding to these trajectories is shown in Fig. 4e, where small squares (summer release) and diamonds (winter release) indicate the positions of the particles every 6 months. The vectors of time-averaged currents at mooring FSW and FSE (Hattermann et al., 2021) are shown in the highest (black arrow) and lowest (blue arrow) instrument levels. A straight black line shows the position of the vertical transect (f) of vertical velocity.

The particles remaining on the shelf are drawn into the circulation under the FRIS, accompanied by an outflow of water through the Hughes Trough to the Belgrano Bank, where a topographic eddy is formed (see Fig. 3a) and through the Filchner Trough. A sudden increase in the depth of both trajectories is observed at 1800 km from the source (highlighted in Fig. 4a and 4c by red circles). A horizontal Z-shaped motion of the particles in the Filchner Trough accompanies this vertical change. These trajectories are shown in greater detail at higher resolution in Fig. 4e. The trajectories are coloured according to particle depth. The explanation for this particle behaviour is that the current changes direction to the south near the island’s eastern coast. This is accompanied by downward vertical velocity at 79-80 °S, as shown in the vertical transect of the year-averaged vertical velocity in Fig. 4f. The position of this transect on the map is depicted in Fig. 4e as a black straight line. Accordingly, particles drift relatively slowly east and downward, then return to move along the central Filchner Trough. The presence of a southerly flow does not contradict time-averaged data at mooring FSW in the highest (black arrow) instrument levels.

Fig. 5: (a) ARGO floats trajectories at the Bransfield Strait from the first cycle, 15 March 2025. (b) Virtual particle release locations.

The particles seeded in the sector adjacent to the Larsen Ice Shelf have almost all left the source area. In addition, the seasonal distribution of the mixed layer thickness showed that winter convection covers the shelf and continental slope in the FRIS sector. In the shelf sector adjacent to the Larsen C Ice Shelf, the thickness of the mixed layer does not exceed several tens of meters due to the presence of freshened waters coming from the melting of the ice shelf. About 29% of all released particles dived below 1000 in the eastward flow, including 3% and 26 % of FRIS and Larsen particles, respectively. At the same time, only 2% of released particles descended below 1000 m at 58°W equally from FRIS and Larsen release sectors. This means that the pathways of particles strongly depend on the location from which these particles were released.

2.1.2 Lagrangian pathways in the Bransfield Strait

The Bransfield Strait (BS) is located between the South Shetland Islands (SSI) and the western coast of the Antarctic Peninsula (AP). The Weddell Sea water enters BS from the northern opening of BS, whereas Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) enters through passages between SSI. Two-way water exchange occurs in BS: the Bransfield Current (BC) flows along the eastern coasts of SSI, while the Antarctic Coastal Current (ACoC) transports Weddell Sea water along the western coast of AP. Mesoscale variability dominates in separating BC from the ACoC front. This makes BS a key area in exchange processes between the Weddell and Bellingshausen seas. A significant amount of field research in this region of Antarctica has been conducted using drifters; however, the first study of current trajectories, temperature, and salinity was initiated in March 2025, when NASC launched six ARGO floats (Fig. 5a).

Fig. 6: Visitation frequency and representative trajectories (white dots) from location 5 in the Bransfield Strait in February and August at the surface and a depth of 350 m.

Therefore, a preliminary Lagrangian pathway analysis of circulation in the BS was conducted using Copernicus database data on circulation, temperature, and salinity around the AP. These data, obtained from the NEMO model simulation with 10 km resolution, were cycled for the year 2024 to track particles using the Lagrangian model Parcels. Particles were released from 9 locations at two cross sections in the BS at the surface and at a depth of 350 m (Fig. 5b). In each location, 31,000 particles were released during 14 days in February and August. The pathways of water masses were characterised by calculating Lagrangian statistical parameters: the visitation frequency and the representative trajectory. These characteristics are given for two sources in locations 3 and 5. As shown in Figs. 6 and 7, the representative trajectories align well with the distributions of visitation frequencies. The representative trajectory of the virtual particle released from location 5 in February at the surface passes to the west of SSI. In contrast, the trajectory of the particle released at a depth of 350 m remains in the BS following BC. The trajectories and visitation frequencies also depend on the release season. As seen in Fig. 7, the virtual particle released from location 3 in February initially moves west along BS, then makes a U-turn and returns to the BS entrance. However, particles released at location 3 in August do not enter the strait; instead, they flow north-eastward both on the surface and at 350 m depth.

Fig. 7: Visitation frequency and representative trajectories (white dots) from location 3 in the Bransfield Strait in February and August at the surface and a depth of 350 m.

2.1.2 Ice keel-induced breaking of internal solitary waves: impact on mixing

The pressure ridging of marine ice forms underside ridges (keels) and ridges above sea level (sails). The keels (Fig. 8a), which extend to depths of tens of meters, can significantly impact the hydrodynamics and thermodynamics of the upper layer of the polar oceans. In particular, interactions between internal solitary waves (ISWs) and ice keels are a factor influencing mixing processes in the upper polar ocean, where ice cover plays a dominant role in modulating heat and salt fluxes. The role of the keels in this interaction, on the one hand, consists of generating ISW when currents and tidal flows are disturbed by the keels (Zhang et al., 2022a). On the other hand, an ISW that travels beneath the ice cover can lose stability when exposed to keels, leading to mixing and increased heat and mass exchange between the ice and the ocean (Zhang et al., 2022a; Terletska et al., 2024). These processes intensify ice melting and help refresh the upper layer of water.

Our study aimed to assess the impact of ridging zones and the distribution of keels at different scales on the efficiency of under-ice mixing in ice-melting processes. The numerical simulations were carried out using a non-hydrostatic model (Maderich et al., 2012). The numerical model used here is based on the Reynolds-

averaged Navier–Stokes equations in the Boussinesq approximation for a continuously stratified fluid. The Smagorinsky turbulence model, extended to stratified fluids, was used to explicitly describe small-scale turbulent mixing in ocean-scale ISWs. The numerical experiments were carried out in an idealised 2D setup (Fig. 8b). The model was initialised using the iterative solution of the Dubreil-Jacotin-Long (DJL) equation.

Fig. 8: (a) Observed ice draft variability of ice ridging as extracted from MOSAiC data versus idealised ice draft distribution; (b) Sketch of the numerical configuration for simulation of ISWs transformation under groups of ice keels.

Table 2: Average geometric characteristics of ice keels in the Arctic and Southern Oceans.

Variable	Arctic (Strub-Klein and Sodom, 2012)	Antarctic (Tin and Jeffries, 2003)	MOSAiC winter (Anhaus et al., 2025)	MOSAiC summer (Anhaus et al., 2025)
Level ice thickness (m)		0.75	1.2	1.3
Maximum ice keel depth (m)	8.2	3.7	6.1	6
Keel width (m)	33.6	27	40.1	36.7
Keel angle (°)	26	15	19.5	18

Modelling of the ISW and ice keel interaction requires information on keel geometry, temperature and salinity profiles, and ISW characteristics. The geometric attributes of first-year ice keels in the Arctic and Southern Oceans are given in Table 2. In the Arctic Ocean, keels tend to be deeper and wider than in the Antarctic. The mean keel width for polar oceans was approximately 30 m. Our wavelet analysis of recent ice keel high-resolution survey data collected within the MOSAiC project, which utilised a multi-beam sonar installed on a remotely operated vehicle, revealed that the mean keel width can be separated into two distinct classes. In the first class, the keel width was 30-40 m in summer and winter. In another class, the zone of pressure ridging can be much larger, ranging from 60 to 110 m.

Fig 9: (a) The snapshots of the density field for an incident ISW passing under the ice ridge with 13 keels (a) and 7 keels (b); Energy loss vs ratio of ISW wavelength λ to the ridge scale L_k (c).

Another result of high-resolution measurements was the discovery of fine structure in ridging zones with “sub-keels” of several-meter scale (Fig. 8a), which contribute to ridge roughness and enhance mixing by ISW. Therefore, we considered the interaction of ISW with the ice ridge, consisting of a group of keels, as shown in Fig. 9a and 9b. As seen in the figure, except for the ISW wavelength λ and the horizontal scale of the ridge L_k , it depends on the distance between keels. When this distance is relatively large, then ISW generate secondary waves of the second mode. When the distance is short, then the vortices in the troughs are generated, enhancing mixing. In more detail, the last process is described in Fig. 10. We compared the laboratory experiment (Carr et al., 2010), in which the propagation of ISW-elevation over the corroborated bottom when $\lambda/L_k \gg 1$. Note that graph 9a is shown upside down. Figure 9b shows the results of the calculations for the individual keel scale. As shown in Fig. 10, the vortices were caused by the propagation of the ISW, similar to that observed in both the simulation and the laboratory experiment. In both cases, vortices were generated in the troughs, thereby enhancing mixing.

The normalised energy loss is defined as

$$E_{loss} = \frac{E_i - E_{tr} - E_{ref}}{E_i}$$

where E_i , E_{tr} , and E_{ref} are incoming, transmitted, and reflected pseudoenergies of ISW. The dependence of energy loss on the wavelength, number of keels in the ice ridge of length L_k is given in Fig. 9b. As seen in the figure, shorter wavelengths relative to keel length led to more intense wave–keel interactions, resulting in enhanced wave breaking, vortex formation, turbulent dissipation, and sea ice melting. Similarly, a shorter keel-to-keel distance at a fixed horizontal scale of the ridge enhances ISW dissipation.

Fig. 10: Comparison of laboratory experiment (Carr et al., 2010) with simulation at the ratio of ISW wavelength λ to the keel scale l_k equal 9.5. The plate (a) shows a side view of the experiment, whereas the plate on the right shows a zoom of the area marked by the green rectangle.

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2.3 Open Science

Software

The source code of the Parcels model can be downloaded from github.com/OceanParcels/parcels. Installation instructions and detailed tutorials for working with the <http://www.oceanparcels.org> are available on the website: <http://www.oceanparcels.org>

The kernels developed in this work are openly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17192869>.

Datasets

The data underlying this deliverable are deposited in Zenodo, available in open access, with a tag pointing to 'OCEAN ICE'. The DOI is the following: <https://zenodo.org/records/17186946>

Peer-reviewed publications

Bezhenar, R., Maderich, V., Brovchenko, I., Boeira Dias, F. Äijälä, C., & Uotila, P. (2024). Lagrangian pathways connecting the Weddell and Bellingshausen Seas. *Ukrainian Antarctic Journal*, 22(2), 163–171. <https://doi.org/10.33275/1727-7485.2.2024.734>

The modelling results were communicated via the following presentations at scientific conferences and workshops:

- Bezhenar, R., Maderich, V., Brovchenko, I., Boeira Dias, F. Äijälä, C., & Uotila, P. Lagrangian pathways connecting the Weddell and Bellingshausen Seas. EGU General Assembly 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-7289>
- Bezhenar, R., Maderich, V., Brovchenko, I., Connectivity of currents between the Weddell and Bellingshausen seas from the Lagrangian point of view. Book of Abstracts. XII International Antarctic Conference, Kyiv, Ukraine, May 13–14, 2025
- Terletska, K., Maderich, V., and Urbancic, G.: Impact of ice keel geometry on internal solitary wave dynamics, EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr–2 May 2025, EGU25-3131, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-3131> 2025.
- Terletska, K., Maderich, V. The impact of ice keel geometry on internal wave dynamics and mixing processes in polar regions. Book of Abstracts. XII International Antarctic Conference, Kyiv, Ukraine, May 13–14, 2025.

3. Results

The particle tracking model Parcel was modified to describe, for the first time, the Lagrangian transport of water masses beneath ice shelves. For the first time in oceanography, we utilised a characteristic of water mass transfer known as representative trajectories, which are the individual particle trajectories that deviate least from the rest. Unlike other characteristics, representative trajectories allow us to characterise circulation in areas with complex bottom relief and coastal topography.

An analysis of the behaviour of representative trajectories in the Filchner trough revealed unusual behaviour of virtual particles, which suddenly increase in depth at a distance of 1800 km from the source. This “dive” is accompanied by a horizontal Z-shaped motion of the particles. The explanation for this trajectory behaviour is that the current changes direction to the south near Berkner Island’s eastern coast.

The proportion of particles that turn to the Bellingshausen Sea from Filchner-Ronne and Larsen shelves is 21% of the total number of particles, while 70% turn northeast, and the proportion of remaining on the shelf is 9%. The farther to the west, the more particles are captured by the strong ACC. So, only 3.4% of the particles were transported west of 80°W, while only 0.1% reached the Amundsen Sea (105°W). This indicates a lack of connectivity between the Weddell and Amundsen Seas circulation. In the Bransfield Strait, the representative trajectories align well with the distributions of visitation frequencies. They demonstrate essential dependence on both the release season and the release depth.

The wavelet analysis of recent high-resolution ice keel survey data collected within the MOSAIC expedition, which utilised a multi-beam sonar installed on a remotely operated vehicle, revealed that the mean keel width can be separated into two distinct classes. In the first class, the keel width was 30-40 m in summer and winter. In another class, the zone of pressure ridging can be much larger, 60-110 m.

Based on the results of measurements of the geometry of the fine structure of ridging zones by the ROV, we included in the consideration the fine structure of the ridging (see Fig. 8a). It was found that, along with ISW wavelength λ and the horizontal scale of the ridge L_k , it depends on the distance between “sub-keels”. When this distance is relatively large, then ISW generates secondary waves of the second mode. When the distance is short, then the vortices in the troughs are generated, enhancing mixing. As seen in the figure, shorter wavelengths relative to keel length led to more intense wave-keel interactions, resulting in enhanced wave breaking, vortex formation, turbulent dissipation, and sea ice melting. Similarly, a shorter keel-to-keel distance at a fixed horizontal scale of the ridge enhances ISW dissipation.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following project objective, as described in the description of the action.

O10: Resolve the structure and temporal evolution of the seasonal exchanges between cold Weddell Sea waters and relatively warmer central West Antarctic Peninsula waters.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by modelling the connectivity of currents around the Antarctic Peninsula and identifying the seasonally varying structure of flows carrying virtual particles from the Eastern to Western Antarctic Peninsula continental shelves through the Bransfield Strait. Modelling indicates a lack of connectivity between the circulation in the Weddell and Amundsen Seas. We also applied particle tracking for the first time to the flows beneath the ice shelves of the Weddell Sea, revealing unusual behaviour of virtual particles in the Filchner Trough, which makes a Z-like turn between Berkner Island and the continent. The new concept in the field of oceanography, Lagrangian characteristic, representative trajectory, was introduced.